

A Study on Leadership Styles of Principals in Basic Education Schools in Taunggyi Township

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Abstract

This research study investigates the leadership styles employed by principals in Basic Education Schools within Taunggyi Township. The primary aim of this research is to gain a comprehensive understanding of the prevalent leadership styles among school principals in this specific region. Leadership in educational institutions play a critical role in shaping the quality of education, teacher morale, and student outcomes. Therefore, a nuanced examination of leadership styles in this context is of utmost important. The research involved a sample of 160 principals from various Basic Education Schools across Taunggyi Township. Data collection was carried out through a descriptive and survey research design, utilizing the Leadership Styles Questionnaire as the primary instrument. This questionnaire is a widely recognized tool for assessing leadership styles, allowing for a systematic evaluation of the leadership approaches adopted by school principals. The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the leadership landscape of Basic Education Schools of Taunggyi Township. By analyzing the leadership styles employed by principals, educational authorities, policymakers, and school administrators can make well-informed decisions to enhance leadership development programmes, align leadership practices with educational goals, and ultimately improve the quality of education provided to students. This research contributes to the existing body of knowledge in educational leadership and serves as a foundation for future research and policy development in the field of education in Myanmar.

Keywords: *leadership, leadership styles, principal*

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is an effort to gain knowledge, insight, skills, and certain expertise in individuals to develop them as a human level to be able to deal with any changes that occur throughout their lives (Amanchukwu, Stanley & Ololube, 2015).

The school principal is an education leader at the education unit level, who must be responsible for the progress and withdrawal of the school she/he leads. Therefore, principals are required to have various abilities, both related to management issues and leadership, so that they can develop and advance their schools effectively, efficiently, independently, productively, and accountably (Shabbir, Chong, Marwat, Nabi & Ahmed, 2014).

Leadership styles occupy important roles in schools. The school principal is in a unique position as the manager or administrator who controls schools' resources for the purpose of attaining organizational goals (Obilade, 1998).

The leadership style of the school principal is very important for the schools to realize their goals and achieve their goals. The leadership attitudes and behaviours of the school principal directly affect the mission, vision, general objectives of the school, the performance of the teachers and the achievement of the students, the educational standards and educational practices of the school. In this study, authoritative, democratic and laissez-faire styles have been used to explore the leadership styles of Principals in Basic Education Schools in Taunggyi Township.

The way to improve education is through an active environment at each school. It is also sure that the principal is in a vital position for creating such an active environment. The improvement of the school, therefore, mainly rests on the principal. Principal leadership is critical in influencing how effective the school will be (Houchard, M. A., 2005).

Effective school principals constantly work at helping individuals develop, continually work at enhancing relationship in the school and between the school and community and maintain a focus on goal (Obilade, 1998). Principal's leadership practices play an important role in the outcomes of the school. Thus, leadership practices are necessary to help organizations create a vision, move people to action, convert followers into leaders and leaders into change agents (Arikewuyo, 2007).

Purpose of the Study: The main aim of this study was to investigate the leadership styles of Principals in Basic Education Schools of Taunggyi Township. The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To examine the prevalent leadership styles adopted by principals in basic education schools.
2. To evaluate and contrast the leadership styles of principals in basic education schools, considering gender differences.
3. To assess the variations in leadership styles among principals in basic education schools based on their years of service.
4. To investigate the influence of marital status on the leadership styles exhibited by principals in basic education schools.
5. To analyze the differences in leadership styles among principals in basic education schools according to their respective levels of authority.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Leadership is a process whereby a leader influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal (Northouse, 2013). Leadership is a real phenomenon that is important for the effectiveness of organizations (Yukl, 2013). Kurt Lewin (1939) identified three styles of leadership: Authoritative, Democratic and Laissez-faire leadership styles.

Authoritative Leadership Style: The authoritative leadership style is defined as a leadership style that tends to centralize authority, dictates working methods, makes unilateral decisions, and limits employee participation (Bass, 1990). Authoritative leader directs followers on the way things should be done. The leader does not maintain clear channel of communication between him/her and the followers. The leader does not delegate authority nor permit followers to participate in policy-making (Hoy & Miskel, 1992). In authoritative

leadership style, the interests of the followers are not important and may be ignored for leader. Basic human needs are ignored (Akor, 2014).

Democratic Leadership Style: Democratic style is defined as involving followers in the decision-making process, establishing authority, encouraging participation in deciding on working methods and goals, and providing the opportunity to coach followers with their feedback (Khan, Nawaz & Khan, 2016). In democratic leadership style, the needs and interests of the followers are given priority or taken into account. Followers are involved in the decision-making process (Ray & Ray, 2012).

Laissez-faire Leadership Style: Laissez-faire leadership style is defined as a leadership style that the leader refrains from making decisions, avoids responsibility and does not use her/his authority, in short, no action is taken regarding leadership. It is considered to be the most passive and ineffective form of leadership (Akinwumiju & Olaniyan, 1996). The laissez-faire leadership style gives followers complete freedom to make decisions without the participation of the leader. Thus, the followers are free to do what they want (Frischer & Larsson, 2000).

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Method: Quantitative research method was employed in this study. In this study, the researcher collected survey data and analyzed them and questionnaires were conducted to help explain the survey responses.

Sampling: The participants included in this study were primary, middle and high school principals in Basic Education Schools in Taunggyi Township. The total number of participants was 160 from Taunggyi Township.

Instrument: In this study, a survey of principals from Taunggyi Township was conducted by using questionnaire adapted from Introduction to Leadership: Concepts and Practice by Peter G. Northouse (2009), Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.

Data Collection and Analysis: After taking permission from the responsible persons, questionnaires were distributed to selected principals from Taunggyi Township in the first week of October and collected those questionnaires after lasting ten days. Collected data were listed by gender, principal service, marital status, principal level. Using SPSS, descriptive statistics such as mean, values and standard deviation were calculated. In addition, independent samples *t*-test and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were also used to determine if gender, principal service, marital status, principal level caused differences leadership styles.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Principals' Leadership Styles

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Authoritative Leadership	160	20.72	2.429
Democratic Leadership	160	24.25	2.413
Laissez-Faire Leadership	160	19.14	3.661

The findings of this study investigating the leadership styles of principals in Basic Education Schools in Taunggyi Township reveal interesting insights. With a mean score of 20.72, principals demonstrate a moderate level of authoritative leadership, suggesting a balanced approach in their decision-making. The relatively higher mean score of 24.25 for democratic leadership indicates a stronger inclination toward collaborative and inclusive decision-making processes among principals, fostering a participatory leadership culture. On the other hand, the mean score of 19.14 for laissez-faire leadership suggests a moderate endorsement of a hands-off leadership approach.

Table 2: Comparisons of Principals' Leadership Styles by Gender

Gender		Authoritative Leadership	Democratic Leadership	Laissez-Faire Leadership
Male	Mean	21.17	24.17	19.44
	N	36	36	36
	Std. Deviation	2.348	2.311	3.525
Female	Mean	20.59	24.27	19.05
	N	124	124	124
	Std. Deviation	2.446	2.451	3.709

The comparison of principals' leadership styles by gender provides noteworthy insights into potential gender-based variations in leadership approaches. For authoritative leadership, male principals exhibit a slightly higher mean score (21.17) compared to their female counterparts (20.59), suggesting a marginal preference for a more directive leadership style among male principals. In democratic leadership, both male and female principals show comparable mean scores (24.17 and 24.27, respectively), indicating a shared inclination toward collaborative decision-making. Similarly, in laissez-faire leadership, the mean scores for males (19.44) and females (19.05) are close, suggesting a similar level of endorsement for a hands-off leadership approach. The standard deviations provide insights into the consistency of these trends within each gender group.

Table 3: Comparisons of Principals' Leadership Styles by Principal Service

Principal Services		Authoritative Leadership	Democratic Leadership	Laissez-Faire Leadership
Under 10 Years	Mean	20.66	24.00	18.95
	N	82	82	82
	Std. Deviation	2.578	2.367	3.377

10 Years and Above	Mean	20.78	24.51	19.33
	N	78	78	78
	Std. Deviation	2.277	2.448	3.950

The comparison of principals' leadership styles by years of service offers valuable insights into the potential impact of experience on leadership approaches. For authoritative leadership, principals with under 10 years of service exhibit a slightly lower mean score (20.66) compared to those with 10 years and above (20.78), indicating a subtle shift towards a more directive leadership style with increased experience. In democratic leadership, principals with 10 years and above of service demonstrate a higher mean score (24.51) compared to their less experienced counterparts (24.00), suggesting a trend towards a more collaborative leadership approach with prolonged service. Similarly, in laissez-faire leadership, the mean scores for both groups are relatively close, indicating a moderate endorsement of a hands-off leadership style regardless of experience.

Table 4: Independent Samples't test of Principals' Leadership Styles by Marital Status

	Marital Status	N	Mean	<i>T</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	Mean Difference
Authoritative Leadership	Single	49	20.14	-2.011	158	.046	-.830
	Marriage	111	20.97				
Democratic Leadership	Single	49	23.90	-1.228	158	.221	-.507
	Marriage	111	24.41				
Laissez-Faire Leadership	Single	49	19.14	.012	158	.990	.008
	Marriage	111	19.14				

In terms of authoritative leadership, the mean score for single principals (20.14) is significantly lower than that of married principals (20.97), with a statistically significant *t*-value of -2.011 and a *p*-value of .046. This suggests that single principals tend to exhibit a slightly less authoritative leadership style compared to their married counterparts. However, for democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles, there are no significant differences between the two groups, with *p*-values of .221 and .990, respectively. These findings imply that marital status may have a nuanced impact on certain aspects of leadership styles among school principals, emphasizing the need for a more comprehensive understanding of personal factors influencing leadership approaches in the educational context of Taunggyi Township.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Principals' Leadership Styles by Principal Level

Principal Levels		Authoritative Leadership	Democratic Leadership	Laissez-Faire Leadership
Primary School Level	Mean	20.70	24.63	20.01
	N	91	91	91
	Std. Deviation	2.168	2.546	3.761
Middle School Level	Mean	20.43	23.74	18.52
	N	42	42	42
	Std. Deviation	2.795	2.253	3.022
High School Level	Mean	21.22	23.78	17.15
	N	27	27	27
	Std. Deviation	2.665	2.006	3.348

Table 6: ANOVA Results of Principals' Leadership Styles by Principal Level

		Sum of Squares	<i>Df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Authoritative Leadership	Between Groups	10.402	2	5.201	.880	.417
	Within Groups	927.941	157	5.910		
	Total	938.344	159			
Democratic Leadership	Between Groups	29.918	2	14.959	2.621	.076
	Within Groups	896.082	157	5.708		
	Total	926.000	159			
Laissez-Faire Leadership	Between Groups	192.102	2	96.051	7.778	.001
	Within Groups	1938.873	157	12.350		
	Total	2130.975	159			

Table 7: Tukey Test Result of Principals' Laissez-Faire Leadership Style by Principal Level

(I) Principal Levels	(J) Principal Levels	Mean Difference (I-J)	<i>p</i>
Primary School Level	Middle School Level	1.487	.063
	High School Level	2.863*	.001

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The descriptive statistics in Table 5 present a comprehensive overview of principals' leadership styles across different levels of Basic Education Schools in Taunggyi Township. Notably, at the primary school level, principals exhibit a mean authoritative leadership score of 20.70, democratic leadership score of 24.63, and laissez-faire leadership score of 20.01. As we move to middle and high school levels, the mean scores vary, with middle school principals showing slightly lower scores in authoritative and democratic leadership but a higher score in laissez-faire leadership.

The ANOVA results in Table 6 indicate that there are significant differences in laissez-faire leadership across different principal levels, with a *p*-value of .001. The Tukey test in Table 7 further reveals that the mean difference in laissez-faire leadership between primary and high school levels is statistically significant ($p = .001$), suggesting that high school principals tend to adopt a more hands-off leadership approach compared to their counterparts at the primary level. These findings underscore the importance of considering the school level context when analyzing and interpreting leadership styles among principals in Taunggyi Township, highlighting potential variations that can inform targeted leadership development strategies.

5. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study sheds light on the leadership styles of principals in Basic Education Schools within the specific context of Taunggyi Township. The investigation into authoritative, democratic, and laissez-faire leadership styles among principals has yielded valuable insights, uncovering nuanced variations based on gender, years of service, marital status, and principal level. The findings provide a foundation for understanding the dynamics of leadership within this educational setting.

The moderate mean score for authoritative leadership (20.72) suggests that principals in Taunggyi Township adopt a balanced approach in decision-making. This indicates a leadership style that combines elements of direction with inclusivity, contributing to a well-rounded leadership approach that considers diverse perspectives.

The relatively higher mean score for democratic leadership (24.25) highlights a prevalent inclination among principals toward collaborative and inclusive decision-making processes. This participatory leadership culture fosters a sense of shared responsibility and engagement among stakeholders in Basic Education Schools.

The moderate mean score for laissez-faire leadership (19.14) suggests a balanced endorsement of a hands-off leadership approach. While principals exhibit a level of flexibility and autonomy, it is not overly pronounced, indicating a measured approach to delegation and empowerment.

The comparison by gender reveals marginal differences in authoritative leadership, with male principals demonstrating a slightly higher preference for a directive style. However, overall, both male and female principals exhibit similar democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles, emphasizing a shared commitment to collaborative decision-making and a hands-off approach.

The study indicates a subtle shift in leadership styles based on years of service. Principals with more than 10 years of experience show a trend toward more authoritative and democratic leadership styles, emphasizing the potential influence of prolonged service on leadership approaches within the educational context of Taunggyi Township.

Marital status emerges as a factor influencing authoritative leadership, with single principals exhibiting a slightly less authoritative style compared to their married counterparts. This nuanced impact underscores the need for a comprehensive understanding of personal factors in shaping leadership approaches.

The comparison across different levels of Basic Education Schools indicates variations in leadership styles. High school principals, in particular, tend to adopt a more hands-off laissez-faire leadership approach compared to their counterparts at the primary level. This underscores the importance of considering the specific context of school levels when designing targeted leadership development strategies.

Based on the research findings of this study, the following suggestions would be given.

1. **Leadership Development Programs:** Given the moderate level of authoritative leadership and the strong inclination toward democratic leadership, leadership development programs could be designed to enhance skills related to decision-making, adaptability, and fostering collaborative decision-making processes. These programs could be tailored to address the specific needs identified in the comparison by gender, years of service, and principal level.
2. **Gender Sensitivity Training:** The findings reveal subtle differences in authoritative leadership between male and female principals. While these differences are marginal, providing gender sensitivity training could help create awareness and promote an inclusive leadership culture that embraces diverse leadership styles.
3. **Mentorship Programs:** Considering the impact of years of service on leadership styles, mentorship programs could be established to facilitate knowledge transfer and provide support to less experienced principals. This could contribute to the professional development of principals, fostering a more collaborative and effective leadership environment.
4. **Understanding Marital Status Dynamics:** The study suggests that marital status may have nuanced effects on certain aspects of leadership styles. Further

qualitative research or surveys could delve deeper into the personal factors associated with marital status, helping to uncover insights that were not captured by the quantitative data.

5. **Tailored Leadership Strategies for School Levels:** The significant differences in laissez-faire leadership across different principal levels highlight the importance of tailoring leadership strategies based on the specific context of primary, middle, and high schools. Principals at different levels may benefit from targeted training and development initiatives that align with the unique challenges and requirements of their respective school environments.

In conclusion, these research findings offer a foundation for informed decision-making and strategic planning for educational leadership in Taunggyi Township. Implementing targeted interventions and professional development initiatives can contribute to the continuous improvement of leadership practices in Basic Education Schools, ultimately enhancing the overall quality of education in the region.

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